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Supporting multi-objective natural small water retention measures planning: the Cherio river basin case study, Italy

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SUMMARY

Endine Lake

Diversion

Outlet

What is the optimal planning of Natural Small Water Retention Measure implementation to increase the basin's hydrological resilience?

SUMMARY

SWAT + model

NSWORMs integration

Optimization
(NSGA-II)

Python

Output
statistical
analysis

R-Shiny

Optimization's output

ABSTRACT

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Title

INTRODUCTION

STUDY AREA: **Cherio River Basin**

Agro – Forested basin located
North-East of Milan

BASIN FEATURES

CRITICAL ASPECTS & OBJECTIVES

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BASIN FEATURES

- **Extension:** 153 Km²
- **Elevation:** 1376 – 141 m a.s.l.
- **A.A. Precipitation:** 1200 mm
- **Cherio River length:** 30 km
- **Land Use:** 42% forest, 39% pasture, cropland
- **Soil:**
SW section: deep, scarce skeleton, fine texture
NE section: shallow, abundant skeleton, coarse texture

Introduction

CRITICAL ASPECTS & OBJECTIVES

Area main hydrological issues: **Floods and drought**

Can be tackled by

NATURAL

Use or imitate
nature

SMALL

Field –scale,
headwaters

WATER RETENTION

Effects on water quantity
and quality

MEASURES

Structural or
practice change

What are the best territorial planning solutions?

OBJECTIVE: to identify the optimal levels of NSWRM implementation in the Cherio River Basin

Introduction

NSWRMs catalogue

METHODS

MODEL CONFIGURATION

SWAT + model setup

**Contiguous Objects
connectivity approach**

Tool:

- SWATbuild.R
- SWATfarm.R

SWAT + model calibration

Tool:

- SWATtun.R

NSWRMs IMPLEMENTATION

NSWRMs identification:

- Terrace
- Pond
- Constructed wetland
- Buffer
- Drought resistant crop

NSWRMs implementation

Tool:

- SWATmeas.R

OPTIMIZATION

OBJECTIVES:

- Environmental
- Economical

Tool:

- Constrained Multi-objective Optimization of Land use Allocation (CoMOLA)
- Pareto_Pick.R

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NSWRMs IMPLEMENTATION

NSWRMs locations

TERRACE:

POND:

BUFFER:

C. WETLAND:

DROUGHT R. CROPS

Methods

NSWRMs IMPLEMENTATION

TERRACE:

% of basin total surface: 19

POND:

% of basin total surface: 1.8

BUFFER:

% of basin total surface: 0.9

C. WETLAND:

% of basin total surface: 8

DROUGHT R. CROPS

% of basin total surface: 20

Methods

Assessment of NSWORMs effectiveness

OPTIMIZATION

OBJECTIVES:

- **Minimize max flows:** reduction of a. a. peak flows to avoid flooding
- **Maximize min flows:** increment of a.a. minimum flows to maximize irrigation water availability
- **Minimize NSWORMs costs:** minimize implementation and maintenance costs of NSWORMs
- **Maximize Agr. Gross Margin:** maximizing the agriculture productivity of the area

Python NSGA-2

Output visualization, Statistical Analysis

ParetoPick-R (R-Shiny app)

CoMOLA

Methods

RESULTS

Best Solutions TO CLUSTERS

NSWRMs Costs (euro)

Agr. Gross Margin (euro)

Status Quo

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Clusters (k-means)

Results

Clusters (k-means)

Results

Clusters (k-means)

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Cluster 1

Cluster variation to status-quo

A.A. Max Flows	-37.1%
A.A. Min Flows	+13.8%
NSWRMs Costs	11 mln
Agr. Gross Margin	+201.2%

Individual measures' share in total considered area

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Cluster 2

Cluster variation to status-quo

A.A. Max Flows	-34.6%
A.A. Min Flows	+14.0%
NSWRMs Costs	0.1 mln
Agr. Gross Margin	+0.7%

Individual measures' share in total considered area

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Cluster 3

Cluster variation to status-quo

A.A. Max Flows	-29.0%
A.A. Min Flows	+15.5%
NSWRMs Costs	24 mln
Agr. Gross Margin	+392%

Individual measures' share in total considered area

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Cluster 4

Cluster variation to status-quo

A.A. Max Flows	-36.2%
A.A. Min Flows	+17.1%
NSWRMs Costs	24 mln
Agr. Gross Margin	+249%

Individual measures' share in total considered area

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CONCLUSIONS

- All four clusters, representative of all the optimal solutions, successfully achieve the environmental objectives with minimal variation among them; the main difference lies in the economic indicators. This suggests that a potential decision-maker may retain a certain degree of flexibility in choosing whether or not to invest in the area's productivity, while still achieving equivalent environmental benefits.
- Certain types of measures, such as buffer strips and constructed wetlands, appear to be the most promising compared to others, as they are the most frequently implemented across all four clusters.
- The future development of this study involves organizing a MARG meeting with various stakeholders from different categories, in order to concretely propose territorial solutions that represent sound compromises among their diverse needs.
- Finally, due to its flexibility, the optimization approach adopted in this study, could be extended to other applications: adoption of different indicators, climate change scenarios optimization, and integration with other models.

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